

Supportive Care and Antibiotics for Severe Pneumonia among Hospitalised Children (SEARCH): A Pragmatic Randomised Controlled Trial

Statistical Analysis Plan

1. Introduction

Pneumonia is the leading infectious cause of death among children. Inpatient mortality among children with severe pneumonia often exceeds 10%. For more than 30 years, World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines have recommended empirical treatment with a combination of injectable benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin for children at the highest risk of mortality (severe pneumonia). There is growing debate over the appropriateness of the current recommendations for empirical treatment. The first key question this trial seeks to address is whether either injectable amoxicillin-clavulanic acid or ceftriaxone is superior to benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin (standard care) for the treatment of children hospitalised with severe pneumonia.

Some authorities advise against enteral nutrition in severely ill patients, citing concerns of compromised respiratory status and increased risk of aspiration with nasogastric feeding. Evidence to support these concerns is lacking. Further, administration of intravenous fluids demands careful monitoring - a common challenge in many low resource settings. Intravenous fluids are also deficient in nutritive value to match the raised metabolic demands associated with acute illness. The second key question is therefore whether nasogastric feeding is superior to intravenous fluid therapy for supportive management of children with severe pneumonia

SEARCH is a 3x2 factorial pragmatic randomised controlled superiority trial. The factorial design allows for the testing of the two questions and two randomisations will be made; the first to one of the three antibiotic regimens and the second to nasogastric feeding vs. intravenous fluid therapy.

2. Hypotheses

(i) Mortality amongst children admitted to hospital with severe pneumonia is not altered by administration of either intravenous amoxicillin/clavulanic acid or ceftriaxone as first-line treatments compared to the standard WHO-recommended treatment (benzyl penicillin or ampicillin and gentamicin).

(ii) Mortality amongst children admitted to hospital with severe pneumonia is not altered by administration of enteral nutrition via the nasogastric route as immediate supportive therapy compared to intravenous maintenance fluids.

3. Outcomes

Primary outcome

The primary outcome is mortality at five days.

Secondary outcomes

- (i) Safety as defined by any serious adverse events likely or definitely related to intervention.
- (ii) Length of hospital stay
- (iii) Duration taken to tolerate full fluid requirements by mouth
- (iv) Mortality 30 days after enrolment

4. Sample Size

The proposed sample size is 4392. We estimate cumulative mortality at Day 5 in the reference groups (penicillin / gentamicin or intravenous fluids) to be approximately 12%, based on data from local studies (1,2) including an observational study of >3000 children with severe pneumonia hospitalised at the proposed study hospitals (3).

With 4182 participants enrolled, the study will have 90% power to detect a 30% relative reduction in mortality (4% absolute reduction) across the antibiotic intervention groups with a two-tailed alpha fixed at 2.5% to allow for multiple comparisons. This calculation is based on the clinical assumption of no interaction between the two interventions (antibiotics and nasogastric feeds/intravenous fluid therapy). The same sample size will allow for the detection of a relative reduction in mortality as low as 25% (3% absolute reduction) in the nasogastric feeds against the intravenous fluid therapy treatment arm (assuming baseline mortality of 12%, two-tailed alpha also set at 2.5%, and after exclusions are applied).

A previous clinical trial that recruited children with pneumonia at some of the proposed study sites reported inpatient loss to follow up of <1% (4). Given the severe presentation of the target study population, we have provided an allowance of 5% for drop-outs.

5. Randomisation

The random allocation sequence will be computer-generated at the KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme according to a block randomisation list of random block sizes for each site. At each site, a study computer will be programmed with the random allocation sequence (separately assigned for each of the two randomizations shown in Figure 1). This will be done in a secure manner to avoid any possibility of viewing the allocation sequence. The study clinical officer at each site will enter the patient's details into the computer and only then will the allocation will be revealed. The site will revert to random allocation using the next numbered sealed opaque envelope as the back-up option if the computer-based randomization fails.

6. Trial flow chart

Data on the number of children randomised (with exclusions and reasons for exclusion), the flow of children through enrolment, allocation to intervention, follow-up and analysis will be presented in a flow chart (5).

7. Data Sets

4.1 Analysis levels

Statistical analysis will be carried out at the individual level. The two interventions (antibiotics and supportive care) will be analysed separately

4.2 Intention-to-treat and per-protocol datasets

Analyses will be carried out using two different types of dataset.

- i) The intention-to-treat datasets: Data will be analysed based on children according to the random allocation irrespective of whether the intervention was or was not entirely or partly taken up.

- ii) The per-protocol datasets: As it is possible that children may not receive the intervention, the intention to treat analysis might underestimate the potential effectiveness of intervention. A per-protocol analysis will therefore be carried out in addition to the intention-to-treat analysis. The per protocol datasets will include data pertaining to all outcomes, restricted to those children who complied with their assigned intervention.

The primary analysis will use the intention-to-treat datasets.

Although intention-to-treat analysis is recognised as the gold standard approach to the analysis of randomised controlled trials, per-protocol analyses can be useful additions to assess efficacy, especially when non-compliance is thought not to be associated with the intervention.

8. Demographic and Other Characteristics

Tabulation of demographic and other characteristics will be done using the intention-to-treat datasets. No significance tests will be performed to test for differences at baseline. Descriptive statistics for continuous variables will include the mean, standard deviation, median, range and the number of observations. Categorical variables will be presented as numbers and percentages.

Enrolment level baseline characteristics of children will be tabulated by marginal treatment arm in line with the factorial design of the trial and the assumption of no interaction between antibiotic treatment and feeding. (Dummy table 1)

Table 1 Participant characteristics by treatment arm

Characteristics	Antibiotic			Supportive Care	
	A	B	C	X	Y
History					
Sex					
<i>Male</i>					
<i>Female</i>					
Age (months)					
Re-admission					
Discharged <1 month					
Weight (kg)					
Height (cm)					
WHZ					
MUAC (cm)					
Length of illness (days)					

Difficulty feeding					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Pre-admission Antibiotics					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
<i>Don't know</i>					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
<i>Don't know</i>					
Temperature (degree Celsius)					
Respiratory rate (bmp)					
O2 saturation (%)					
Central Cyanosis					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Indrawing					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Grunting					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Wheeze					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Crackles					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Capillary refill (/secs)					
Pallor Anaemia					
<i>0</i>					
<i>+</i>					
<i>+++</i>					
Can drink / breastfeed					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Diagnoses					
Malaria					
<i>Severe</i>					
<i>Non-severe</i>					
<i>None</i>					
Diarrhoea					
<i>Bloody</i>					
<i>Non-bloody</i>					
<i>None</i>					

Dehydration					
<i>Shock</i>					
<i>Severe</i>					
<i>Some</i>					
<i>None</i>					
HIV					
<i>Positive</i>					
<i>Negative</i>					
<i>Exposed / PMTCT+</i>					
<i>Declined test</i>					
Malnutrition					
<i>Kwash</i>					
<i>Marasm</i>					
<i>M.Kwash</i>					
<i>Moderate malnutrition</i>					
<i>Mild/none</i>					
Anaemia					
<i>Severe</i>					
<i>Non-severe</i>					
<i>None</i>					
Sickle cell disease					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Meningitis					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Rickets					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					
Asthma					
<i>Severe</i>					
<i>Mild/moderate</i>					
<i>None</i>					
Suspected TB					
<i>Yes</i>					
<i>No</i>					

9. Measurements of Compliance with the intervention

Data on actual management will be collected in all arms of the trial. (Dummy table 2).

Table 2: Treatment compliance

Table 2a Antibiotic treatment non-compliance and reasons

	Antibiotic		
	A N= n(%)	B N= n(%)	C N= n(%)
Changed antibiotic			
Reason			
<i>Change of diagnosis</i>			
<i>Treatment failure</i>			
<i>Senior review</i>			
<i>Consent withdrawn</i>			
<i>Other</i>			

Table 2b Supportive care method non-compliance and reasons

	Supportive Care	
	X N= n(%)	Y N= n(%)
Changed feeding method		
Reason		
<i>Vomiting</i>		
<i>Suspected aspiration</i>		
<i>Failed IV access</i>		
<i>Consent withdrawn</i>		
<i>Other</i>		

10. Effectiveness and Tabulations of Patient Data

10.1 Analysis of effectiveness

10.1.1 Primary analysis of the outcome(s) will follow the intention to treat principle.

For the primary outcome, log binomial models will be used to estimate the risk ratio for five day mortality between children receiving injectable amoxicillin-clavulanic acid and benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin (standard care) and also to estimate the risk ratio for five day mortality between ceftriaxone and benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin (standard care). Similarly log binomial models will be used to estimate a risk ratio for five day mortality between children receiving nasogastric feeding and children receiving to intravenous fluid therapy. We will report risk ratios associated 95% confidence intervals. (Dummy Table 3).

For mortality 30 days after enrolment (secondary outcome) for intervention versus control treatments log binomial models will be used to examine the effect of the relevant intervention. Risk ratios will be reported with 95% confidence intervals. (Dummy tables 3.).

Outcomes

Table 3a Primary and secondary outcomes by antibiotic treatment arm – Factorial Analysis

	Antibiotic		
	A n(%) RR (95% CI)*	B n(%) RR (95% CI)*	C n(%) RR (95% CI)*
Mortality at 5 days	X(%) 1	X(%) X.XX (X.XX- X.XX)	X(%) X.XX (X.XX- X.XX)
Mortality at 30 days			
Experienced SAR			
	A Mean(SD) HR (95% CI)*	B Mean(SD) HR (95% CI)*	C Mean(SD) HR (95% CI)*
Length of hospital stay			

**Adjust for a priori confounders: age, sex, site*

Table 3b Primary and secondary outcomes by supportive care treatment arm – Factorial Analysis

	Supportive Care	
	X n(%) RR (95% CI)*	Y n(%) RR (95% CI)*
Mortality at 5 days	X(%) 1	X(%) X.XX (X.XX-X.XX)
Mortality at 30 days		
Experienced SAR		
	X Mean(SD) HR (95% CI)*	Y Mean(SD) HR (95% CI)*
Length of hospital stay		
Duration to tolerate full fluid requirements by mouth		

**Adjust for a priori confounders: age, sex, site*

Other secondary outcomes: length of hospital stay and duration taken to tolerate oral feeds, will be analysed using Kaplan-Meier plots and the hazard ratios with accompanying 95% CI calculated using Cox proportional hazards regression

10.1.2 Secondary analysis of outcomes will use the per protocol datasets and the same statistical analysis techniques as in 10.1.1.

Additionally we will consider a complier average causal effect (CACE) analysis will also be carried out (6). The CACE analysis will estimate a measure of the effect of the intervention on those participants who received it as intended by the original allocation. Although intention-to-treat analysis is recognised as the gold standard approach to the analysis of randomised controlled trials, a CACE analysis is a useful addition to assess effectiveness.

10.1.3. Examination of Subgroups

Pre-specified subgroup analyses will be conducted by HIV status and the following clinical characteristics: nutritional status, age (infants versus older children), presence or absence of malaria and presence or absence of pallor.

10.2 Statistical/analytical issues

10.2.1 Adjustments for Covariates

Adjustment for variables (site gender and age) will be made in the primary analysis. In addition, any major imbalances between randomised groups in prognostic factors will be adjusted for in exploratory secondary analyses.

10.2.2 Dropouts and Missing Data

The data coordinating centre at KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme will be responsible for logging all data as they arrive and contacting the sites about any missing data. Missing data will be chased until received, confirmed as not available, or the trial is at analysis. Data quality, follow up and trial monitoring will be facilitated through the development of a trial specific database, including validation, verification, monitoring and compliance reports and follow up report functionalities. Therefore only a small amount of missing data is expected and it is not thought likely that it will have to be accounted for in any analysis. Sensitivity analyses will however be conducted for the primary outcome. We would consider using inverse probability weighting if missing data were larger than expected and/or there was differential attrition between the trial arms. We would also attempt ensure that the reason for the differential attrition was fully understood.

10.2.3 Outliers

Any unusual values/potential outliers will be queried following the process outlined in the Trial Data Management Plan. If the value is found to be correct then it will be included in all analyses.

10.2.4 Protocol deviations

Deviations from the randomised treatment will be noted and tabulated (Table 2). Analyses will be undertaken as described in section 4.2.

10.2.5 Interim Analysis and Data Monitoring

An independent Data Safety and Monitoring Board (DSMB) will be established to review, in strict confidence, data from the trial approximately every six months. The Chair of the DSMB may also request additional meeting/analyses. One scheduled interim analysis will be performed by an independent statistician once approximately half of the total sample size is achieved. In the light of these data and other evidence from relevant studies, the DSMB will inform the Steering Committee if in their view :

- i. There is proof that the data indicate that any part of the protocol under investigation is either clearly indicated or clearly contra-indicated either for all patients or a particular subgroup of patients, guided by the stringent Peto-Haybittle rule (7,8).
- ii. It is evident that no clear outcome will be obtained with the current trial design.
- iii. That they have a major ethical or safety concern

10.2.6 Multiple Comparisons/Multiplicity

The sample size calculations used an alpha of 2.5% to allow for the multiple comparisons between antibiotic treatment arms. However as the number of secondary outcomes that will be tested for significant differences between arms is small no further formal adjustment for multiple comparisons will be made.

10.2.7 Rules for derived variables

Categorisation of variables will be detailed in XX

11. Safety Evaluation

Information of all adverse events and deaths will be collected and reported in both arms of the trial. SAEs that are deemed probably and definitely causally related to the study drug and SUSARs will be initially reported to the local study monitor, DSMB, and the

ethical review committees (SERU, PPB-ECCT and OXTREC) within 48 hours of the investigators becoming aware of the event with a follow up report being provided within a further five working days. A summary of all other SAEs and suspected toxicity events will be reported every 3 months. The report will include the site; study number; date of event; subject details (initials, sex and age); nature of event; relevant history; outcome and a judgement of causality.

Full details on Adverse Events and Safety Reporting are given in section 12 of the trial protocol

12. References

1. Webb C, Ngama M, Ngatia A, Shebbe M, Morpeth S, Mwarumba S, et al. Treatment Failure Among Kenyan Children With Severe Pneumonia—A Cohort Study. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 2012;
2. Agweyu A, Kibore M, Digolo L, Kosgei C, Maina V, Mugane S, et al. Prevalence and correlates of treatment failure among Kenyan children hospitalised with severe community-acquired pneumonia: a prospective study of the clinical effectiveness of WHO pneumonia case management guidelines. *Trop Med Int Heal* [Internet]. 2014;19(11):1310–20. Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/tmi.12368>
3. Agweyu A, Lilford RJ, English M, Irimu G, Ayieko P, Akech S, et al. Appropriateness of clinical severity classification of new WHO childhood pneumonia guidance: a multi-hospital, retrospective, cohort study. *Lancet Glob Heal*. 2018;6(1):e74–83.
4. Agweyu A, Gathara D, Oliwa J, Muinga N, Edwards T, Allen E, et al. Oral amoxicillin versus benzyl penicillin for severe pneumonia among Kenyan children: A pragmatic randomized controlled noninferiority trial. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2015;60(8).
5. CONSORT; www.consort-statement.org
6. Dunn G, Maracy M, Tomenson B. Estimating treatment effects from randomised clinical trials with non-compliance and loss to follow up: the role of instrumental variable methods. *Stat Methods Med Res* 2005;14;369-96
7. Haybittle JL: Repeated assessment of results in clinical trials of cancer treatment. *Br J Radiol* 1971, 44(526):793-797
8. Peto R, Pike MC, Armitage P, Breslow NE, Cox DR, Howard SV, Mantel N, McPherson K, Peto J, Smith PG: Design and analysis of randomized clinical trials requiring prolonged observation of each patient. II. analysis and examples. *Br J Cancer* 1977, 35(1):1-39